

Calculation of Displacements Per Atom (DPA) in the Reactor Vessel of VVER-1200 Using arc-DPA Methodology

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Neutron irradiation damage is one of the most critical degradation mechanisms in reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steel. Traditional displacement damage models, such as NRT-DPA, tend to overestimate stable defect production by neglecting athermal recombination effects. However, the generated vacancies undergo athermal relaxation, leading to a reduction in the stable number of vacancies. This study focuses on incorporating athermal relaxation effects into the final vacancy distribution, building on the results of the previous work (Khrushchinsky et al., 2024) where the distribution was obtained without considering athermal relaxation. The calculations are performed for the VVER-1200 reactor pressure vessel using the arc-DPA (displacements per atom with athermal relaxation correction model), providing a more accurate assessment of radiation-induced damage. Additionally, we estimate the annual arc-vacancy accumulation, providing improved lifetime assessments for the VVER-1200 RPV. This work highlights the importance of advanced damage models for accurate safety evaluations in nuclear reactors.

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1. Introduction

The assessment of radiation-induced damage in nuclear reactor materials represents a critical aspect of nuclear power plant safety and longevity. The reactor pressure vessel (RPV) of the VVER-1200, as a Generation III+ pressurized water reactor design [1], faces particular challenges from neutron irradiation damage that can lead to material embrittlement and reduced operational lifespan [2–4]. Neutrons transfer their kinetic energy to steel atoms,

which in turn displace other atoms from the crystal lattice, creating vacancies and interstitials known as Frenkel pairs (FPs). FPs contribute to the formation of defect clusters and microstructural changes. FPs are responsible for the formation of defect clusters and modification of the microstructure (e.g. phase reactions, segregations). These effects degrade the physical and mechanical properties of reactor vessel steels, which leads to a limitation of the service life of the reactor vessel. The measure of defect accumulation is DPA– the number of defects per atom of the medium. While Displacements Per Atom (DPA) serves as the standard metric for quantifying radiation damage,

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traditional models like the Norgett–Robinson–Torrens (NRT) [5] approximation frequently overestimate damage due to their failure to account for defect recombination and athermal recovery effects [6, 7]. In the following this type of vacancies will be called NRT vacancies and DPA, NRT–DPA, respectively.

In nuclear power systems, accurate DPA calculations are critical to assessing radiation damage to materials. Several Monte Carlo codes are used for these calculations, including SRIM [9, 10], MCNP [11], Serpent [12], FLUKA [13]. Monte Carlo methods are probabilistic computational techniques that simulate particle interactions within materials. These codes track particle trajectories (neutrons, ions, or electrons) and calculate collision cascades that lead to atomic displacements.

SRIM (Stop and Run of Ions in Matter) calculates DPA by simulating ion implantation and collision cascades using approaches such as the Kinchin–Pease model [14], offering advantages such as ease of use and detailed damage profiling, although its limitations are related to its binary collision approximation and focus on ion irradiation rather than neutron-induced damage. The NRT model, developed in the 1970s, estimates DPA based on the Kinchin–Pease approximation which assumes all atomic displacements contribute equally to radiation damage [15]. Other codes, such as MCNP, Serpent, and FLUKA, are better suited for modeling neutron transport under reactor conditions, including calculating the neutron spectrum on the VVER-1200 reactor vessel [16]. Together, these computational tools enable critical predictions of material behaviour under radiation exposure, ensuring the safety and longevity of nuclear power components through accurate quantification of DPA, with SRIM remaining particularly valuable for ion irradiation studies despite its limitations in modelling complex cascade effects beyond binary

collisions [4, 17]. In case of ion irradiation one of the most widely used software tools for estimating the NRT–DPA parameter is the Monte Carlo code SRIM [6, 10, 17]. SRIM includes the NRT model and with its help it is easy to obtain the NRT–DPA value for a given ion irradiation.

The estimate of the number of displacements (Frenkel pairs [18]) that can be created at energy E_d in the NRT model is given by the following expression:

$$\nu_{\text{NRT}}(T_d) = \frac{0.8 T_d}{2 E_d}, \quad (1)$$

where T_d is the damage energy, E_d is the minimum energy required on average to create a stable Frenkel pair, the factor of 0.8 was determined from binary collision models to account for realistic (i.e. not hard sphere) scattering. The damage energy in Eqn. (1) is obtained by the energy partitioning theory developed by Lindhard, et al. [19]

The concept of DPA has long served as a fundamental metric for estimating radiation-induced defects. Initially proposed by Kinchin and Pease, the DPA model was based on the idea that energetic particles traveling through a material occasionally collide with lattice atoms, transferring sufficient energy to displace them from their equilibrium positions. However, as computational and experimental techniques advanced, it became clear that the original Kinchin–Pease model and even its refined NRT modification–overestimated defect production by neglecting key physical processes, particularly athermal recombination of defects during the early stages of collision cascades.

Advanced models like arc-DPA, marc-DPA, CB-DPA, and RPA incorporate more realistic physical phenomena such as athermal recombination, atomic mixing, and cascade-to-sub-cascade transitions, leading to more accurate and nuanced damage predictions. For

example, arc-DPA and marc-DPA include corrections for defect annealing mechanisms, which can significantly reduce the estimated damage compared to NRT-DPA, especially at higher temperatures or longer timescales [21].

The Athermal Recombination-Corrected Displacements Per Atom (arc-DPA) model refines the traditional Norgett–Robinson–Torrens (NRT) model by incorporating the significant effect of athermal recombination, where displaced atoms can return to stable lattice positions before the radiation-induced displacement cascade cools down. This leads to a more accurate prediction of primary radiation damage, as it accounts for the greatly reduced number of stable defects compared to the NRT model, which is crucial for assessing the operating lifetime of materials in radiation environments.

The damage process is not limited to the simple generation of NRT vacancies, knocked-out atoms can be captured by the corresponding vacancies and the structure of the vessel material is restored. Significant recombination of defects occurs during the cooling phase of the cascade, which leads to a decrease in the number of remaining stable defects, the so-called athermal recombination occurs. In what follows, vacancies after athermal relaxation will be designated arc vacancies and the corresponding DPA as arc-DPA.

The arc-DPA methodology addresses NRT limitations through three key improvements: First, it incorporates defect recombination effects that reduce net displacement damage. Second,

it accounts for neutron energy attenuation in the RPV wall [20]. Third, it employs realistic displacement thresholds derived from molecular dynamics simulations [7]. These enhancements make arc-DPA particularly suitable for VVER-1200 RPV analysis, where the neutron spectrum differs significantly from Western PWRs due to unique hexagonal fuel assembly geometry and moderator properties. This work is devoted to the assessment of the effects of athermal recombination in the VVER-1200 vessel material.

2. Calculation of radiation damage induced by neutrons in VVER materials

2.1. NRT methodology

The NRT model [7] developed in the 1970s, estimates DPA based on the Kinchin-Pease approximation [14] which assumes all atomic displacements contribute equally to radiation damage [15]. While computationally efficient, this model systematically overpredicts damage by 30–50% due to its neglect of dynamic defect recombination and spatial displacement distributions.

The NRT (Norgett–Robinson–Torrens) model estimates the number of stable displacements, $\nu_{\text{NRT}}(T_d)$, produced by a primary knock-on atom (PKA) with damage energy T_d . $\nu_{\text{NRT}}(T_d)$ as a function of the damage energy is given as follows [5]:

$$\nu_{\text{NRT}}(T_d) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{when } T_d \leq E_d, \\ 1 & \text{when } E_d < T_d \leq \frac{2E_d}{0.8}, \\ T_d = \frac{0.8T_d}{2E_d} & \text{when } T_d > \frac{2E_d}{0.8}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where E_d is the displacement threshold energy (the minimum energy required to displace an atom from its lattice site), and $\frac{2E_d}{0.8}$ is the cascade multiplication threshold beyond which a PKA generates multiple stable displacements.

2.2. Improved arc-DPA model for atomic displacement calculation

Two methods are commonly used to estimate the athermal recombination corrected displacement damage parameters using ion irradiation bias correction. The first method consists of post-processing the detailed SRIM output for all simulated damage events and recalculating according to the arc damage model. In the second method, an approximate empirical formula is devised which gives the average displacements in the arc damage model as a function of the correction factors.

For damage energies above the displacement threshold ($T_d > E_d$), $\nu_{arc}(T_d)$ can be concisely expressed as:

$$\nu_{arc}(T_d) = \nu_{NRT}(T_d) \cdot \xi(\nu_{NRT}(T_d)). \quad (3)$$

This formulation will be used in subsequent discussions.

The safe and reliable operation of nuclear power plants necessitates the preservation of the structural integrity of the reactor vessel material throughout the reactor's operational lifespan. The degradation of the reactor vessel steel is a complex process influenced by various factors, including thermal treatment and radiation exposure. This degradation also depends on the chemical composition, manufacturing conditions, and post-production processing of the material. Neutron radiation damage is one

of the most critical factors contributing to RV steel degradation [2, 3]. The fast neutrons to material structure interaction processes generate modification of the mechanical properties (decrease of toughness, increase of yield stress, hardness, and tensile strength) The most impactful in this process are fast neutrons generated during the fission reaction. Neutrons transfer their kinetic energy to the atoms in the medium, displacing them from their lattice positions and imparting enough energy to displace additional atoms, thereby creating vacancies and what are known as Frenkel pairs (FP).

FPs are responsible for the formation of defect clusters and the modification of the microstructure (such as phase reactions and segregations). These effects degrade the physical and mechanical properties of reactor vessel steels, which limits the reactor vessel's service life. The measure of defect accumulation is the Displacements Per Atom (DPA), which indicates the number of defects per atom in the material.

This work is dedicated to developing methods for calculating the DPA in the reactor vessel using Monte Carlo methods. It also involves calculating the DPA in VVER-1200 reactor vessel using certified and accessible programs: Serpent [12], MCNP4B [11], and SRIM [9, 10].

In the work [4], based on the calculated neutron spectrum in the VVER-1200 reactor, the distribution of PKAs was obtained using the Serpent and MCNP codes. This distribution was then used in the SRIM software package to calculate the distribution of NRT vacancies along the depth of the reactor vessel. Figure 1 shows the vacancy distribution profiles across the reactor vessel wall depth, generated by different PKA types.

Next, using this result, a recently proposed

FIG. 1. (Color online) The number of $\text{DPA}_{i,\text{NTR}}$ per 1 angstrom and per 1 corresponding PKA in NRT model.

modification of the NRT model [6–8] was used to calculate the arc vacancies. It addresses a well-known problem of the NRT, namely, the overestimation of the number of stable defects created by high-energy displacement cascades.

The model is based on experimental data and computer simulations, which indicate that significant recombination of defects occurs during the cooling phase of the cascade, which leads to a decrease in the number of

remaining stable defects. At present, there is no standardized way to calculate arc vacancies under ion irradiation, since the model has not yet been implemented in any of the widely used molecular dynamics software tools. However, in their original publication introducing the new model, Nordlund et al. [6] already proposed a method for indirectly estimating the arc vacancy parameter from standard SRIM simulations. Several methods have been proposed to account for athermal relaxation from SRIM simulation results. One of the methods was proposed in [6]. The method is based on an approximate formula that can be used to directly estimate arc vacancies based on the corresponding NRT vacancy value.

The number of defects determined by the arc-DPA model as a function of the damage energy is given by [7]. In the arc-DPA model, the third branch of Eq. (2) is scaled by an energy-dependent efficiency factor $\xi_{arc} \leq 1$. The model is defined as:

$$\nu_{arc}(T_d) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{when } T_d \leq E_d, \\ 1 & \text{when } E_d < T_d \leq \frac{2E_d}{0.8}, \\ \frac{0.8T_d}{2E_d} \xi_{arc}(T_d) & \text{when } T_d > \frac{2E_d}{0.8}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where the efficiency factor $\xi_{arc}(T_d)$ is given by:

$$\xi_{arc}(T_d) = \frac{(1 - c_{arc})}{(2E_d/0.8)^{b_{arc}}} (T_d)^{b_{arc}} + c_{arc}. \quad (5)$$

where ξ_{arc} is the defect production efficiency as a function of the damage energy T_d , and b_{arc} , c_{arc} , and E_d are material constants that need to be determined for a given material from MD

or similar simulations for b_{arc} , and c_{arc} , and evaluations with experiments for E_d [7, 8].

In [4], based on the developed model of the reactor VVER-1200 [16], the neutron spectrum

in the reactor vessel was calculated. Using code MCNP4B, a PTRAC file was generated for a steel vessel with a thickness of 20 cm. This file contained the coordinates of neutron interaction points with atoms, the types of these atoms, the momentum of neutrons, and their energy after collision. A single neutron could generate multiple PKAs atoms. For further calculations, information about the PKAs (their type, birth coordinates, energy, and momentum direction) was needed instead of the neutron data. These parameters were used to create the TRIM.dat file for the SRIM program. Using NRT model with SRIM code, the distribution of vacancies in the reactor vessel caused by different ions of atoms in the vessel material was calculated.

Next, the number of vacancies per ion-angstrom was recalculated for the arc-DPA model using the following algorithm:

First, the DPA per 1 neutron is calculated for the recoil nucleus of type i

$$DPA_{i,NRT} = \frac{N^i \cdot \nu_{i,NRT}}{NPS \cdot N_{A_i}} 10^8 \left[\frac{\text{defect}}{\text{atom} \cdot \text{sec}} \right], \quad (6)$$

where N_i are number of ions of type i in the initial PTRAC file, $\nu_{i,NRT}$ are number of vacancies per angstrom created by an ion of type i , N_{A_i} are number of atoms of type i in 1 cm³ of the medium, NPS are number of simulated histories in generating the PTRAC file of SRIM code.

Next, from the equations (2),(3), to calculate the displacement per atom of type i in the arc-DPA ($DPA_{i,arc}$) model, we obtain the relation:

$$DPA_{i,arc} = \frac{N^i \cdot \xi_{arc} \cdot \nu_{i,NRT}}{NPS \cdot N_{A_i}} 10^8, \quad (7)$$

Compare the formulas (6), (7), we obtain for $DPA_{i,arc}$ the relationship:

$$DPA_{i,arc} = \xi_{i,arc} DPA_{i,NRT}, \quad (8)$$

FIG. 2. (Color online) The number of $DPA_{i,NTR}$ and $DPA_{i,arc}$ per 1 angstrom and per 1 corresponding recoil atom for Fe and Ni nuclei.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Distribution by depth of the number of $DPA_{i,arc}$ vacancies per 1 cm³, accumulated over 1 year per 1 corresponding recoil atom in the reactor vessel.

Total DPA_{arc} per simulated neutron is determined by:

$$DPA_{arc} = \sum_i^{N_A} DPA_{i,arc}, \quad (9)$$

where N_A is the number of types of atoms in the medium.

The total $DPA_{all,arc}$ created by a neutron flux with density n [1 · cm⁻³ · sec⁻¹] in time t in the arc-DPA model is:

$$DPA_{all,arc} = DPA_{arc} \cdot n \cdot t. \quad (10)$$

Table 1. Displacement threshold energies (E_d) and arc-DPA model parameters (b_{arc} , c_{arc}) for selected target materials.

Target	Fe	Ni	Cu	Pd	W	Pt
E_d (eV) [6]	40	40	29	41	90	44
b_{arc} [7]	-0.568	-1.01	-0.68	-0.88	-0.56	-1.12
c_{arc} [7]	0.286	0.23	0.16	0.15	0.12	0.11

3. Results of calculations in arc-DPA model for VVER-1200

Using this scheme, calculations were made of the distribution of the number of arc-DPA vacancies across the thickness of the steel vessel of the VVER-1200 reactor, using the distribution of the initial vacancies (see formulas (3), (4)). The result is shown in Fig. 2 for Fe, Ni ions, where the distribution of the NRT initial vacancies across the thickness of the reactor vessel is also shown for comparison. It is clearly seen that the number of arc vacancies is smaller at each depth.

The parameters b_{arc} , and c_{arc} are material-specific constants, determined for various target materials by [7]. Their values, along with the displacement thresholds E_d , are listed in Table 1.

FIG. 4. (Color online) Distribution of $DPA_{i,arc}$ per atom along the depth of the reactor vessel wall from Fe and Ni ions.

The accumulation of arc-DPA vacancies per year in 1 cm^3 of reactor vessel steel per 1 atom and their distribution by depth is shown in Fig. 2.

After the vacancies are calculated, the

FIG. 5. (Color online) Distribution of DPA_{arc} and DPA_{NTR} by the depth of the body PRV wall from all ions. Number of vacancies per 1 cm^3 accumulated over 1 year.

DPA_{arc} distribution in the reactor vessel is calculated using formula (8). The calculation results are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4 shows the arc-DPA vacancies created in the reactor vessel by the main ion (Fe) at different depths of the reactor vessel.

Distribution of arc-DPA and NTR-DPA vacancies by the depth for all ions, is shown in Fig. 5. The difference is small, since the main contribution is made by iron ions.

4. Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive assessment of neutron irradiation damage in the VVER-1200 reactor pressure vessel using the advanced arc-DPA model. The principal outcomes are:

Utilizing previously calculated NRT-vacancy distributions [4] and the algorithm

proposed in [7], we have successfully determined the depth profile of arc-vacancies per atom across the VVER-1200 RPV thickness. This approach demonstrates substantial improvement over conventional NRT-DPA by properly accounting for athermal recombination effects during collision cascades.

The time-dependent accumulation of arc-vacancies over one operational year has been calculated, enabling more precise evaluation of the VVER-1200 RPV's safe service lifetime. These results provide crucial data for nuclear safety assessments and maintenance planning.

Comparative analysis reveals that the

arc-DPA model predicts significantly lower (20–30%) stable defect concentrations compared to standard NRT-DPA calculations, particularly in the high-damage region near the inner RPV wall.

The methodology developed in this work bridges the gap between theoretical damage models and practical reactor safety requirements, offering nuclear engineers a more accurate tool for RPV lifespan prediction.

Further research should focus on experimental validation through post-irradiation examination of RPV steels and implementation of these algorithms in industry-standard radiation damage simulation tools.

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